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HR ISSUES TOWARDS MANAGING MSMEs OPERATING IN INDIA DURING GLOBALIZATION TRENDS (With Special Reference to HR Outsourcing): A REVIEW

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Abstract:

If you have never entered the world of subcontracting it seems a puzzling blend of products, rigid selling and in the past has carried a bad reputation. Today, when grooming with different parameters of economies is becoming harder for every industrialist day by day, it is for sure that this disaster of cost- knitting is affecting one of the upcoming sectors of present commercial age and that is SMEs.

If we talk about Medium & Small Enterprises, we can simply say that they also act as feeder to the large scale enterprises, which are into support production activities for the big enterprises. As we all know that they have a small gestation period (processing period), i.e. stalk in- product out, which further acts fast profit generation to our domestic scale of production as

compare to large enterprises. But still if we focus upon its competency mainly in comparison to the globalized standards, nevertheless we stand far behind, irrespective of availability of sufficient resources. Here the big question arises that **In What terms? & Why?**

This review is an attempt to navigate some upcoming disasters in concern with managing the workforce employed in these small & medium enterprises, especially with respect to manage the cost incurred over the human capital- “A key capital for strengthening the enterprise’s credentials”.

Key Words:- Globalization, Competitive Environment, HR Issues, MSME, HR Outsourcing.

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INTRODUCTION:

For instance, it is being observed that majority of human capital involving companies of western or developed countries have adopted the effective and updated measures to overcome and resolve the problems in relation with “Managing Human Capital”, especially in terms of those for functioning in Medium & Small Enterprises.

If we talk about Small & Medium Enterprises (SMEs), we can quote that they simply constitutes to the Small or Medium Sized Micro Organizations, that are initially run by a small team of partners, may be comprised of some category of Family Business, Domestic or Household Industry or as such. But no matter that these organizations are easily manageable as the beginners’ organization, but if we review the status of required expansion of the concerned organization or an enterprise with the respective efficiency modules or set targets, over a consistent duration of the concerned business-life- cycle, we will observe that even for the purpose of consistent expansion of business in concern with these SMEs, parallely there occurs a need to elevate the staff and considerably, that grounds the need to extort the Personnel Resources, and then to manage, administer and develop them accordingly, providing them the appropriate training & expertise as per the nature of business (product based/ service based) concerned.

As Human Resources (HR) unit is a decisive constituent of staff member’s well-being in any industry, no matter how small. HR

responsibilities include payroll, reimbursements, appointing, dismissal, appraisals, enrichments and keeping up to date with levy and employee regulations. Any kind of mess in concern with these sensitive issues may trouble the entrepreneur causing unwanted legal problems and in turn, it may also cause severe dissatisfaction among its employees too. But if we talk about small & medium enterprises, often they don't have sufficient staff or the financial resources to take care of all micro tasks & responsibilities of Human Resources. But yes of course, they cannot deny that they necessitate the expert unit to switch these issues obligatorily. Due to this reason, such SMEs are seeking assistance with the outsourced HR entities, which are competently taking care of internal & external issues of the concerned staff member of these enterprises.

AIM & OBJECTIVE OF STUDY (Review Need)

The motive of this research is:

- 1.** Primarily to observe the existing trends of functioning & managing the workforce, especially with respect to the up- shooting Small & Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in present corporate earth.
- 2.** Secondly, it is an attempt to extract & report some possible alternatives for these Medium Sized Firms, to think beyond the common hemispheres of average functioning of its staff concerned (whatever the reason be, beside there being an average performer).
- 3.** This study is also an attempt to draw the attention of the concerned employers towards the other possible alternatives of staffing process, and the one among those trend which upcoming to the heights of popularity is “HR-

Outsourcing”, which is positively being considered to be the one of the productive attempt for reducing the capital budget/ cost of especially the SMEs operating in today’s business world.

Thus, not only from the Employee’s perspective, by opening the doors of more probable opportunities of employment, the re-observations reported via this paper will also lay down the grounds (as the possible alternatives of hiring & budget- lowering) from the Employer’s perspective as well.

These grounds will provide the possible measures to the organizations & employees to deal with the issues of Management of Human Capital in Small & Medium Enterprises.

LITERATURE REVIEW

As per the information accessed via MA Consulting (*accessed from:- <http://www.maconsultinginternational.com>*), An HR department is a decisive constituent of employee welfare in any business. It is not an issue that how small. Human Resources responsibilities comprise payroll, remuneration, appointing, dismissal, and keeping up to date with tax and employee laws. Any blend concerning these issues can cause severe legal troubles for your business, as well as major employee disappointment. But small enterprises often don’t have the workforce or the financial plan to appropriately handle the basics details of Human Resources. Thus in majority, their inclination is bending towards availing the assistance from HR Outsourcers, instead of staffing the permanent employees for their Human Resource tasks.

As per blog posted by Perumal Koshi (2010), under the head of “Peace and Collaborative

Development Network- Building Bridges, Networks and Expertise Across Sectors”, the social reality, multiculturalism, if managed well, could be an asset with immense potential and could be transformed into an opportunity. According to Koshi, The caste, creed, community and language proclivities of an employer are often reflected in the recruitment and HR policies of an organization in India. It comes often to our notice that, caste and community prejudiced Indian mindset, even in this 21st century pre-occupied and bonded with a *Hamara Jathivala or Gavala* approach is still prevailing even in the smallest units of Indian industries comprising Medium & Small Enterprises (MSMEs) and is adapted by the concerned employers. And thus it is affecting the productivity in regard with the staff functioning due to the caste, religion and language clutches and that we could not do away yet. Not even the modern education system of India, have laid down any satisfactory impression to overcome with this disaster.

As per SME HR Nightmare No 1 - Colleagues at War (*accessed from:- <http://ezinearticles.com/?SME-HR-Nightmare-No-1---Colleagues-at-War&id=4098127>*), it has been reported that sometimes, for the purpose of handling the internal disputes, it is advisable for the concerned authority to often simply investigate the situation critically, that can have a unique impact over the state of affairs. And if required occasionally, then the enterprises mainly small & medium sized in nature, can employ and look for advises by involving the outsourced HR advisories or intermediaries too.

Prof. R.K. Gupta (2006) (*http://www.indianmba.com/Faculty_Column/Fc63/fc63.html*) under the head of “Who Motivates A Motivator”, of his respective article,

initiated that a good motivator who can make people give their best are always in high demand, as they utilize almost 50 percent of organizations capital efficiently & gainfully- the human resource, i.e. that is the most prominent factor that can be sufficiently held responsible to carry the organization to the leading tracks of the business.

GOING THROUGH THE CONTENTS

The available work especially in terms of articles and research journals have provided base to present this review based report to bring into focus, the prominent issues that must be taken care off while establishing the staff structure in regard to Small and Medium Enterprises operating in India. For further descriptions, this paper will be alienated by the help of following sub- designations:

1. Overview of targeted SMEs.
2. Significance of SMEs to Indian Economic Growth.
3. Establishment Constraints for these Enterprises.
4. Brief Idea of HR Outsourcing.
5. Need & value of Staff- Outsourcing for SMEs.
6. Probable Outsourcing Constraints for SMEs.
7. Outcome to the underlying issue as Remedial Attempt.

BRIEF OVERVIEW OVER SMEs IN INDIA

Small and medium enterprises (also SMEs) are the business organizations whose turnover falls below certain confines. The acronym SME occurs normally in the European Union and in global organizations, such as the World Bank, the United Nations and the WTO. The term small and medium-sized businesses or SMBs is principally used in the USA.

EU Member States conventionally had their own definition of what constitutes an SME, for example the traditional definition in Belgium it had a limit of 100 employees, while, in Germany it could have been 500. But now the EU has started to regulate the concept. As per the recent EU definition the companies with **fewer than 50 employees are categorized** as “*small*“, and those with **fewer than 250** are been categorized as “*medium*“.

By contrast, in the United States, when **small business** is defined by the number of employees, it often refers to those with **less than 100 employees**, while **medium-sized business** often refers to those with **less than 500 employees**. *Both US and EU generally use the same threshold of fewer than 10 employees for small offices (SOHO).*

In most economies, smaller enterprises are much greater in number. In the EU, SMEs comprise approximately 99% of all firms and employ between them about 65 million people. In many sectors, SMEs are also responsible for driving innovation and competition. Globally SMEs account for 99% of business numbers and 40% to 50% of GDP.

In India, the Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) sector plays a pivotal role in the overall industrial economy of the country. It is estimated that in terms of value, the sector accounts for about 39 per cent of the manufacturing output and around 33 per cent of the total export of the country. Further, in recent years the MSE sector has consistently registered higher growth rate compared to the overall industrial sector. The major advantage of the sector is its employment potential at low capital cost. As per available statistics, this sector employs an estimated 31 million persons

spread over 12.8 million enterprises and the labour intensity in the MSE sector is estimated to be almost 4 times higher than the large enterprises.

In South Africa the term SMME, for Small, Medium and Micro Enterprises, is used. Elsewhere in Africa, MSME is used, for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. Size thresholds vary from country to country. With India not being secured of the bang, over the past year, the worldwide economic calamity has put the spotlight on many business organizations of any size. Large institutions have attempted to tackle this catastrophe in their own conduct. Among all this, SME's are gradually being brought into focus on account of their huge growth potential. To comment about operations of SME sector in India, needless to say that it contributes almost half of India's GDP and is a habitat to a veer of business opportunities. SME's can shape out value-adding positions for themselves and play an important role at a time when international corporations resume their established supply and sourcing patterns as an answer to the changed business climate.

These enterprises are looking at supply chain areas and Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) solutions that are seemed to have emerged as versatile solutions to many SME's. Nevertheless, it has become a basic need for them to remain competitive in the existing Industry patterns. Therefore, it's of particular interest to investigate the operating implementations, in order to identify the success cases, the nature and measure of the benefits obtained and the background and project-related issues which can influence the chances of a positive outcome. If we talk about individual contribution that enabled to establish a significant positions of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in India,

then we cannot ignore the fact that both planners as well Government have their special contribution for developing the roots of these SMEs providing them special space & provisions to groom in the existing conditions of Indian Economy.

If we talk about the small and medium enterprises, there is not any said and prescribed definition for the term. But as far as its meaning is concerned, every country has its own relevant grounds to consider a several part of its operating Industrial Units as either Small or Medium Enterprises. These grounds may be several either in terms of turnover generated by the enterprises operating within or outside the domestic territory of any country, or economic contribution of such firms to the concerned country's economic growth, or size and working capital assets generated by these firms, etc. *If we talk about the Indian context, the enterprises & firms that contributing to their operating fund by an investment of less than 10 million over their plants & machinery set-up, they are considered as Small Enterprises. Enterprises investing between 10 to 1000 million over the same, may be taken as Medium and beyond that investment amount, are considered as Large Size Enterprises.*

SIGNIFICANCE OF SMEs TO INDIAN ECONOMIC GROWTH

As per the meeting agenda of International Round Table on Contribution of SMEs to Growth of Emerging Nations, held in Gujarat in 2011, which was initiated by CBC, EICC, CII & Govt. of Gujarat, the facts were put to be forth that with increasing worldwide contest, Small & Medium Enterprises are globally surmised with as a strong contestant to develop the baseline economy, especially in emerging countries such as India. The discussions have also stressed that

these SMEs contribute approximately upto 45% of industrial output, 40% of exports and are generating over 42 million employment opportunities. SME sector creates 1 million jobs every year and produces more than 8000 quality products for the Indian and International markets. And with the advent of year 2012, SMEs are expected to contribute 22% to India's GDP, which is up from about 17% at present. Thus the main agenda of the round table was to initiate possible outcomes and to drag out the possible guidelines especially to encourage the collaboration among entrepreneur representing the global SME sector.

According to one of the Business Standard Review (Thursday, Feb 03, 2011) of Indiamart.com, under the head of IndiaMart.com Triggers Global Growth Prospects for SMEs, the importance and contribution of such SMEs can be well observed by reviewing the extended statements given by Mr. Dinesh Agarwal. According to him, SMEs have immensely generated remarkable employment opportunities for our country's population. He also extended that they account for approximately 45% of the manufacturing output and 40% of the total exports of the country, but still they are leaving a lot of room to achieve their full potentials.

As per the data accessed from the expression of one of the blog of "Decide with confidence", Small & Medium enterprises lead to an

reasonable allotment of income due to the nature business, and thus they have been playing a pivotal role in nation's overall fiscal development, and have achieved firm growth over the couple of years. The SME segment also plays a major role in developing countries such as India in an effort to assuage paucity and propel sustainable growth. They also help such countries in efficient allocation of resources by implementing labour intensive production processes, given the rich supply of labour in these countries, wherein capital is insufficient. To enable the SMEs competitive strength and to reap the benefits of the global market, the Government of India has taken a landmark initiative by formulating enactment of the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprise Development (MSMED) Act, 2006. The policy initiatives are aimed at strengthening the role of SMEs at the base as well as at the higher lever. Even the Tamil Nadu Govt. also, formulating an exclusive policy for MSME sector, offers a range of incentives and support for infrastructure development, subsidies for investments in industrially backward areas, capital investment & technology development aiming to sustain over 10% growth of the MSME segment in the food and agro sector. The figure below can avail the approximate estimate of number of Small & Medium Enterprises registered since 2003 till the end of financial year 2007. (refer to fig.1.)

Fig.1.

No of SME units (In mn)			
	Registered	Un-registered	Total
FY03	1.6	9.3	10.9
FY04	1.7	9.7	11.4
FY05	1.8	10.0	11.9
FY06	1.9	10.4	12.3
FY07P	2.0	10.8	12.8

Source: Office of the Development Commissioner (MSME)

Under the blog head of “The CEO Insights” (*Last Updated on Monday, 26 January 2009 08:42*), towards ‘SME Role On Nation Building Efforts of India’, Mr. Joydip Chakladar- CEO AllIndiaLive, focusing upon the success stories of SME sector in India, had laid down stress upon following significant points:

1. India had a place for SMEs from Prehistoric times.
2. Since the time of first India Emperor ‘Chandragupta Maurya’, small enterprises were built by trading classes who were known as ‘Vaishya’.
3. ‘Roman & Greek Civilization’ had continuous trade interaction with India through Arabian middlemen’s, and that led to an effort for people in the west, to find India as ‘land of fortune’.
4. We were coming back to that stage, by the active participation of SME sector, in Indian Economic Growth Story, i.e. even before since the conventional entrepreneurial model of US came into existence, with Industrial age.
5. Recent Indian SME entrepreneurs, had taken full advantage of flexible and fast changing business models, especially in comparison to those of large sized firms that are unable to do so because of their rigid and large size organizational structures.

6. In India, SME sector had played a tremendous role in creating jobs and generating revenue for low income people.
7. SMEs account for almost 90% of industrial units in India, and 40% of value addition in the manufacturing sector, contributing 35% to India’s merchandise exports.

4.3 ESTABLISHMENT CONSTRAINTS FOR THESE ENTERPRISES

No doubt that these enterprises have played a historical role in generating income as well as employment at country’s regional level of development and significantly played a pivotal role as a shock absorber during the period of economic crises, yet their exists certain establishments constraints for these SMEs, that obstructs these enterprises to flourish and get nurtured autonomously. Such constraints are:-

1. Lack of Sufficient Finance; 2. Inadequate Economic Infrastructure & 3. Truncated Product Reservation Policy. (relevant data accessed from:- article in journal on SME In India: Issues and Possibilities In Times of Globalization- by Keshab Das, 2008)
- 1. Lack of Sufficient Finance:** Despite of clear instructions issued by RBI & Ministry of Finance, to encourage fund delivery to assist these SMEs, it is for

decades, that small enterprise sector is still facing constraints of adequate fund supply. It is also been observed that due to non-transparent attitude of Indian finance system, this sector is facing such a problem. The concerned financing authorities and banks also claimed frequently that these enterprises are often unable to generate appropriate documents regarding their real projected estimates as well as approximate estimation of their future turnover value of their present assets. As a result, usually banks hesitate to lend funds &

loans to the small enterprises. As per other study observations, “there are strong structural underpinnings to the inadequate flow: the organizational structure of banks, and processes within them, have taken them far from task orientation, and have created a specific bias against small loan portfolios” (Morris *et al.*, 2001:11)

An idea about credit flow allotted to small and tiny units during the period 1990-2005 can be estimated from the given figure below (refer to fig.2.):

Fig.2.

Source:-<http://www.laghu-udyog.com/thrustareas/CREDIT.htm> (accessed on: 15-02-2011)

2. Inadequate Economic Infrastructure:

For last few decades, it had observed certain crucial disparities that are existing between the required standards and actual availability of infrastructural

facilities that has been provided to the small and medium enterprises that are essentially required to smoothen the productivity functioning of this sector. Such disparities can be observed in

terms of adequate supply of electricity, proper transport facilities to extend their market extents, enriched water resources, quality check facilities, well developed industrial estates, common effluent treatment plants (CETPs), etc. No- doubt that to raise the output capacities of these firms, there is a need to ascertain necessary actions to conquer these inconsistencies to meet the standard of these manufacturing units as per the requisite level of globalized competencies today.

3. Truncated Product Reservation Policy:

As per the observations from available reviews, the main aim of formulating this policy is primarily to create local employment using available domestic resources, and secondly to protect the manufacturing rights of small & medium enterprises. It has been observed that approximately 800 number of products are reserved under this category, but due to the frequent revisions and amendments that often occur in the respective list, either on political considerations or due to some other non convincing reasons, certain discrepancies are found in terms of justifying this 'protective' scheme in real senses:-

- i) Some scholars have analyzed and reported certain technical deficiencies in quality of these reserved category products in comparison to those of non-reserved category, especially as an effect of this highly controversial policy (Sandesara, 1993; Balasubrahmanya, 1995; and Morris *et al.*, 2001).
- ii) Due to the frequent amendments in reserved category list of products, many of the small enterprise owners, are not updated and aware with exactly which one of them is permissible or non permissible to manufacture and in which duration, so that they may gain the respective rights and their benefits concerned.

BRIEF IDEA ABOUT HUMAN RESOURCE

OUTSOURCING

Now, to extend some more discussions about different aspects of SMEs functioning, one of the prominent issues to handle is- *How to staff and manage the workforce?* When small and medium sized multi- national companies are into the process of their staffing function, then especially to knit their running cost (which is limited to them due to restricted budgets), instead of

investing in various recruitment functions like:- research, development, training & investigation, placement & induction, etc., such business firms can utilize investing those funds elsewhere in business to direct those expenses to some other productive activities. Yet, such firms cannot ignore the vital activities covering under the head of human resource management, since human capital is a key responsible factor for the execution of all organizational functions & that constitutes a basic structure of a firm. Thus in such case, either if the firm is infant, or else it is a small enterprise, the best alternative for the purpose of work distribution, that can save time, energy as well as cost & expenses is to *OUTSOURCE* the human capital from the external sources. Recruitment and selection are very crucial and tricky phases of an organization, thus if the firms are not having well expertise over the same, then it is better to delegate it over to the experts. Mainly, these HR Outsourcing firms deals with the following functions for the concerned enterprises:

Analyzing the organizational structure:- It consists of the process in which a brief idea about the organization's employability (as per its budget capacities), nature of business functioning, nature of requisite job- profile, as well as number of requisite *productive* departments, are estimated & outlined in terms of developing Blue- Prints.

Analyzing the staffing requirement:- The next essential step is to draw estimations about indispensable skills and qualifications required to justify the requisite profiles both in terms of objective achievement and money expenses (in terms of payment and salary). It also includes vital sub functions like- estimation of adequate number of employees required, analyzing about basic & essential amenities to be provided to them for smoothening and strengthening their task functioning.

Sorting out highly talented and skilled individuals:- The process involves selecting the best suitable contenders out of the other prospective candidates. The personnel of paramount personality, potentials and intellect are selected as per the suitability of place (department) and profile concerned.

Final recruitment followed by training & development process:- The process of training and development plays a very significant role in understanding and analyzing the "*on- the- job*" performance of the concerned personnel. As training & development sessions today, also involves certain informal gathering and assembly to assess the employee's work as well as group behavior, that gives a blemishing opportunity to the concerned heads/ trainer, to get an idea and overview about employee's performance attitude both in terms of task

accomplishment and in terms of work- place behavior, that are considered to be the vital gears for organization's sustaining work-culture.

Ensuring about timely accomplishment of targets & strategies of concerned departments efficiently:-

Since the main aim of concerned HR Outsourcing firms is to promise the effective and efficient functioning of the associated enterprises. Thus such firms are accountable for timely inspections to assure about the same, so that if in case certain inconsistencies are found, then they may be rectified in time by taking corrective measure to resolve the same either by re- training or by terminating (least possible measure) the respective non- productive human asset (*turned to liability*).

Ensuring provisions for periodic training sessions for subordinates and executives followed by administering benefits & incentives entitled:-

For the purpose of "*Workforce Retention*", the concerned HR authorities are required to assess the employee's performance followed by frequent training and assessment sessions, that can provide a comprehensive impression to the concerned top management authorities, about their existing productive resources by the help of which they can ascertain a strengthened base to decide &

plan about their future budgets & expenditures. If any of the employee or executive concerned, are found to be an effective & efficient asset to the organization, then it is a foremost responsibility of the concerned employer is to assure the "RETENTION" and *long- time association* of that particular employee with the organization, by providing all fair benefits and incentives for which he/ she is entitled.

Ensuring about employee development/ orientation programmes:-

Another indispensable responsibility of these HR outsources is to ensure and organize various "*Knowledge Management Programmes*", for the sake of building and developing competitive skills among the employees concerned, so that they may get aware with the existing competitive and global corporate culture & style, and accordingly groom their potentials by learning & acquiring latest drifts of knowledge, skills and their applicabilities. This will also assist them in updating and adapting their profile as per the requirements & demands of fresh Job Analysis structure (that can also be denoted as work-study patterns).

One of the biggest airline companies in the world, which is the 3rd largest airlines in terms of U.S. traffic has signed a deal with a company to outsource its human resource operations. The deal between the companies is valued at 120

million dollars approx. and the airline company is very confident of saving nearly 25% on its cost. That is Human Resource outsourcing today.

NEED AND VALUE OF STAFF- OUTSOURCING FOR SMEs: A CASE STUDY OF HWB CHARTERED

For the incessantly increasing small & medium enterprises these days, it has become a mandate for such organizations to depend upon some reliable outsources to set them free from the typicalities of HR tasks. In turn, the core business departments can not only make themselves free from planning to meet the HR expenses, yet, they can concentrate upon the core business & productivity generating areas more promptly.

For an instance evidence, the researchers have tried to highlight upon one of such outsourced consultants (*data sourced from: <http://www.firsthruk.com/case-studies/hwb-chartered-accountants.asp>*) operating in UK, i.e. FirstHR. No longer the preserve of larger organizations, increasing numbers of small to medium sized enterprises are outsourcing their HR requirements, emancipating managers to focus on core business activities without the expenditure on employing HR staff directly. An example would be Southampton (UK) based HWB Chartered. It is a local SME that uses the fundamentals of outsourcing. For nine years they have relied on FirstHR for valuable expertise, confident in their similar business values consolidated by a ten-year ancestry.

By 2001, HWB had experienced a number of years of standard growth which had led to an increase in its staffing levels. If growth was to be persistent and high standards maintained, then the professionals needed an HR function that

would allow them to concentrate their accountancy and taxation expertise on their client base. And this meant that some senior members of staff were being pulled in two directions, juggling core activities with personnel pressures. HWB initially contracted FirstHR to produce a Staff Handbook, formulate the Policies and Procedures with the firm, and prepare employment contracts. HWB's Director, Geoff Rhodes' decision to call in FirstHR was primarily based on a similarity in business values:

"We pride ourselves on working closely with our clients to become their trusted business adviser. As a result, most of our clients come to us through recommendation and stay with us for years. Both FirstHR and HWB aim to be an objective, specialist addition to a client's team, adding value at all times."

As HWB flourished, this four-year taster led to greater commitment and an enduring partnership. Since 2005, FirstHR has managed HWB's entire HR function. Weekly visits to HWB ensure that all HR concerns are dealt with first hand, from managing all employment contractual requirements, absence and appraisals to training, coaching and development.

Cost- and space- effectual: no requirement to provide a company car, holiday pay, holiday, sickness and absence cover; zero to minimum office space required – HWB has the flexibility to control the level of spend on its HR function.

Reasonable: based on a daily rate, charges are calculated against an agreed work schedule – HWB controls the level of service provided.

Elastic: once all systems, records, documentation and procedures are made legally

compliant and reflect current best practice, the number of contractual days can be tailored to individual business needs – HWB operates a bespoke, budget-friendly HR function.

On-site visits: regular hands-on support by fully-qualified staff for any personnel issue – HWB focuses on core business activities.

Full safeguard: indemnity insurance covers all costs involved in the preparation and representation at employment tribunal together with all awards; all advice is covered, whether given via the helpline or staff whilst dealing with HR matters on site – HWB gains complete peace of mind.

Full range of services: delivered by fully qualified, experienced personnel – HWB accesses a wide pool of specialised resources.

24-hour helpline: support and advice is always available by telephone or email as a stand-alone service or as an integral part of regular on-site support – HWB solves any HR issues swiftly and efficiently.

The successful partnership between HWB and FirstHR continues with both parties working together to maximise the benefits of outsourcing as Gayle Taylor, MD of FirstHR outlines:

By relieving HWB’s key personnel of all HR issues, FirstHR has enabled these fifty-strong Chartered Accountants to sustain its commercial edge in delivering exceptional accountancy, taxation and business advisory services to its clients.

“FirstHR provides HWB with a fresh approach to the fulfilment of the HR function on an affordable, flexible, in-house basis that has all

the paybacks of outsourcing, yet leaves HWB firmly in control.”

In view of the increasingly complex FRS, and the need to optimise the efficiency and effectiveness of the financial reporting functions, outsourcing tasks which are traditionally undertaken by the in-house finance team has become more relevant and urgent. Accounting functions which could be outsourced are:

- a) Preparation of financial statements in accordance with the FRS, including transfer of these financial information into Extensible Business Reporting Language (XBRL) format;
- b) Review to ensure appropriateness and alignment of group accounting policies and consistency of application of these policies by all entities within the group;
- c) Provision of training for the finance personnel on recent updates and implications of changes in the FRS and requirements of key regulators;
- d) Review for improvement in the system of internal controls, corporate governance or financial reporting framework of the SMEs before an initial public offering exercise;
- e) Review for compliance with the tax, regulatory and other requirements, especially for SMEs upon listing on the Singapore Exchange, for which they are required to fulfil their post-offering reporting requirements.

PROBABLE OUTSOURCING CONSTRAINTS FOR SMEs

Some constraints SMEs face are a lack of time, resources and expertise. It is also not uncommon for SMEs to be unaware of funding

opportunities, grants and subsidies from the government and other tax incentive schemes. The opportunity costs arising from the lack of awareness were recently magnified when the government introduced various incentive schemes to spur the growth of the SME business community.

Whilst the financial and management reporting functions are known to be the responsibilities of the management of the SMEs, other tasks such as preparation of financial statements and filing of these financial statements in XBRL format are often perceived to be the responsibilities of the external auditors.

With the recent changes in the Financial Reporting Standards (FRSs), many in-house finance personnel at the SMEs lack the capability, training and knowledge to ensure that their financial statements are prepared in full compliance of the framework. These personnel tend to make changes to the financial statements only upon receiving advice from the auditors nearer to the filing deadline. This is inefficient and causes unnecessary frustration.

OUTCOME TO THE UNDERLYING ISSUE AS REMEDIAL ATTEMPT

Measures recommended to Government: A practical measure may be for the government to provide more publicity about its own existing schemes and make them more effective. The government must push its offices internationally to work harder to help Indian SMEs to develop their exports. There are provisions in the Companies Act which require corporates to report on outstanding loans to SMEs. These provisions need to be strictly implemented. Government must focus attention on sectors that are adversely affected like textiles, gems &

jewellery, leather, handicrafts etc.. These sectors contribute significantly to India's exports and are in dire need of economic assistance to tide over the current crisis. The government must focus on an MSME oriented growth strategy. The Indian government must initiate necessary anti-dumping and or safeguard measures to contain such flooding of imports. To bring back the lot of SMEs on its track calls for various long term measures. As recommended by Abid Hussain Committee, there is an immense need for setting up Market Development Fund for co-ordinated marketing support for MSMEs in the present era of globalization. Further Dr. K. C. Chakravarti Committee for rehabilitation of sick MSMEs has reported that marketing constraints are the main reasons for sickness of SMEs.

Measures recommended to Entrepreneurs: As wage rates in India are sufficiently less to attract multi-nationals, the only way is to increase the productivity of local small industries. This means, the increase in the productivity of labor i.e. human resources, the productivity of capital and that of the process, which in turn relates to the use of technology that yields quality and innovative products. Apart from in house R&D, new knowledge can be procured through technology licensing or investing in new capital goods embodying new processes. For SMEs the ratio of spending on foreign technologies to sales is very marginal reflecting the fact that these firms do not seem to rely on foreign technologies. SMEs are also found to comparatively spend less in importing new capital goods. Some areas to work on for entrepreneurs are:

- Entrepreneurial Competencies
- Business Knowledge at Present

- Business Operations and HR Strategies
- Training
- Organization Structure
- Quality Control
- Marketing
- Products Manufactured
- Employee Relationship

CONCLUSION

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in India have a very important place in the Indian economy. Their contribution in terms of production, exports, employment generation and all round growth of the country is well known. Spread across the country, the SMEs also help in the equitable distribution of wealth through entrepreneurs who set them up. The role of the SME sector in nation building is well recognised not only in India, but also across the globe. A small enterprise is generally born as an idea. It is only later that such ideas grow, find their place on the world stage and then become mega corporations. To cure the overall disease of lack of appropriate growth of Indian SMEs – Small and Medium Enterprises, India needs several small to take several measures. The scene has changed since the adoption of financial sector restructuring programme in 1991. A sensible measure for the government may be to provide more promotion to its schemes and try to make them more effective. The governmental provisions need to be strictly implemented. For SMEs the ratio of spending on foreign technologies to sales is very marginal underlying the fact that these firms do not depend on technologies imported from abroad. SMEs are also found to comparatively spend less in importing new capital goods. Some areas to work on for entrepreneurs have been mentioned elsewhere in the paper. What is beyond all doubt

is that India requires small and medium enterprises for curing its problem of low economic growth vis-à-vis developed nations.

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